

Measuring The Awareness Of Female Teaching Staff Members In Department Of Family Education With The Concept And Methods Of Foreseeing The Future Of The Academic Programs In Light Of The Requirements Of The Vision Of The Kingdom Of Saudi Arabia 2030

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Abstract

Foreseeing the future of education aims to guide educational decisions in order to make optimal use of the available resources; that means improving the level of efficiency in employing public resources in the field of education. As described by Al-Hamid and others (2002 AD), the importance of foreseeing the future of education is increasing with the increasing of the competition among the earth's peoples to gain a head start in the era of globalization and the integrative economy, where capitals are searching for a high-quality educational environment that graduates higher skilled and productive workers and thus guarantees higher returns for investors (Wößmann, 2002 AD).

Therefore, the development of education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has become an urgent necessity for society in all its categories, where the education is the main tool for investing human resources that has become the main element for the economic and social progress, and it is the active element to modernize the ability to keep pace with contemporary and future global developments to shift towards a knowledge economy society (Al-Sayegh, 1999 AD).

The rapid succession of the economic and social changes resulting from globalization, and its impact on society and the labor market, with the increasing demand for university education; It places a greater burden on universities to interact and respond quickly in developing the academic programs with what is suitable for the labor market in light of the vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (Basaid, 2018 AD).

Therefore, teaching staff members must be sufficiently aware of the concept, principles and methods of foreseeing the future in the development of the academic programs, because it is considered one of the important matters that must be given to those responsible for university education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, because they are the foundation and the human axis on which development and improvement depends.

Introduction

Recently, some ministerial decisions were issued that include stopping admission to the integrative educational programs, including art education, family education, physical education, etc., with the development of these programs and changing their names to include the specialized aspect without educational preparation that can be completed through an educational diploma and subsequent educational studies for a degree of Bachelor's degree in the specialization. Although the Education and Training Evaluation Commission report 1441 for the results of tests such as the goals of teachers proved that there is a higher percentage of passing rates and average grades for the graduates of the programs in which educational preparation is carried out in an integrated manner than for the graduates of the sequential programs.

This prompted the need to develop the family education program into a family and consumer sciences program, but the researcher saw that there was a serious mistake in stopping admission to the family education program without a comprehensive study of its importance in achieving the social sustainable development, as this decision was according to one indicator that is employment ratios in the field education for graduates of the program, without considering its contribution to preparing the woman to take care of and manage her family's affairs and bringing up her children, as well as having multiple skills in fashion design, sewing, designing meals, conducting feasibility studies for small projects, and other skills those are necessary for family life and the community . This is from one side.

On the other hand, there were administrative, organizational and financial problems for female teaching staff members, where the lack of teaching shares, which financially affects the members, as well as the courses

available for teaching, and their incompatibility in most cases with some members because their courses have been taught. Therefore, it was important for the responsible authority to anticipate foreseeing the future.

It was important for the responsible authority to foreseeing the future in developing curricula in a sufficient period before the decision to stop admission to the family education program. Therefore, it was necessary to educate and train female teaching staff members about the concepts and methods of foreseeing the future in academic programs, hence the importance of studying measuring the awareness of teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education with the concept and methods of foreseeing the future of the academic programs in light of the requirements of the vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia 2030, for this new entity (the Family and Consumer Sciences Program) is done, which is reflected in achieving the goals of the quality of the academic programs and their effectiveness in meeting the needs of society.

The problem can be summarized in the following question:

To what extent are the faculty members in the Department of Family Education aware of the concept and methods of foreseeing the future when they put forward the proposal of the Bachelor of Family and Consumer Sciences program?

Research objectives:

The current study aims to measure the awareness of female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education with the concept and methods of foreseeing the future of academic programs in light of the requirements of the vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia 2030.

The limits of the study:

The research limits are limited to:

Specialization: Department of Family Education at Al-Leith University College - Umm Al-Qura University.

The target category for the questionnaire: 14 female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education at the University College in Al-Leith for the academic year 1441 AH / 1442 AH.

Research tools:

Using a form to collect the data required for the study

Study approach:

This study follows the descriptive analytical approach through data analysis to measure the awareness of female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education with the concept and methods of foreseeing the future of the academic programs in light of the requirements of the vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia 2030.

Theoretical framework of the study

Foreseeing concept:

The linguistic meaning of foreseeing, as explained by Al-Awwad (1998), carries in its content the meanings of looking at the far object, and trying to identify it, and taking the ways that reach that accurately, such as climbing to a high place that provides a greater opportunity for reconnaissance.

As for idiomatically, according to Ibrahim and others (1989 AD), foreseeing is an organized scientific endeavor that aims to formulate a set of conditional predictions that include the basic features of the conditions of a society, or a group of societies, over a certain period of time. And that is by focusing on the variables that can be changed by issuing decisions, and therefore, foreseeing relates to essential societal issues and employs variables that can be affected by the policy of change.

Considering that foreseeing has become based on more mature scientific methods than before, Al-Sunbul (2003 AD) defined it as "a deep scientific intellectual effort based on quantitative and/or qualitative indicators selected according to the nature of the field of study, and it is intended to predict the future of a particular phenomenon by asking Possibilities and alternatives vary in the degree of possibility of any of them occurring.

Attempts to foreseeing the future are not a product of modern scientific progress, but they are an eternal part of human culture (Al-Sunbul, 2003 AD); And recognizing that the future is among the things that are hidden from humans, and the knowledge of it is with God alone because of His Almighty saying: "Indeed, Allāh has knowledge of the Hour and sends down the rain and knows what is in the wombs. And no soul perceives what it will earn tomorrow, and no soul perceives in what land it will die. Indeed, Allāh is Knowing and Aware" (Luqmān: 34). Humans - with their trust and submission to God - are commanded to strive and plan for the future, and the Messenger of God was planning to build the Islamic state and preparing for it, and he followed the path of his successors after him and the righteous predecessors.

Thus, it appears that foreseeing the future has become a science that has its origins and techniques, and is no longer a stoning of the unseen based on imagination or an abstract sense of scientific methodology. It does not mean being certain about future events - the unseen is known to God alone - but it is based on the logic of possibilities, as we are commanded to work on reading the future and anticipating it with good planning (Al-Rasheed, 1987 AD).

The concept of foreseeing the future of education:

The researchers did not find a specific definition of foreseeing the future of education, but according to studies, foreseeing the future of education can be defined in general as an attempt to predict the future of supply

and demand for education or a particular type of education, whether it depends on the quantitative growth in the values of past and current supply and demand variables or on the personal opinions based on an in-depth reading of the course of events affected by the supply and demand for education.

The importance of foreseeing the future of education stems from the importance of the education itself. People allocate a large part of their scarce resources for education, dreaming that this would contribute to building a better future and achieve the desired prosperity, based on the principle that the most important and best natural resource for the people is their children (Negroponte, 2001AD). But without foreseeing and planning the future of education, then the resources allocated to education may be wasted, and education may turn from a constructive factor into a destructive factor.

Therefore, foreseeing the educational future aims to put perceptions, alternatives, and choices that help the officials and educational decision makers in choosing what is appropriate for next generations of the development in the educational programs.

Foreseeing the future of education acquires a greater importance in countries that suffer from an imbalance in the quality of their educational systems, which is the case of the Arab countries in general (Heyneman, 1997 AD) and Saudi Arabia is no exception. So, the importance of foreseeing the future becomes doubled in countries that have to expand the provision of the educational service quantitatively to meet the increasing demand resulting from the increasing population growth and to improve absorption rates, and Saudi Arabia may be the most obvious example of this, as indicated by the numerous studies and statistical reports ^{1*}.

In order to clarify the general methodology for foreseeing the future of education, Al-Fares (1998 AD) showed that this is done through:

- 1- Analyzing the past trends in population growth and the quantitative development in student numbers and study enrollment rates in order to extract growth patterns and indicators of fertility, mortality rates and migration.
- 2- Making long-term future projections as an important tool for planning and implementing programs and evaluation.
- 3- Analyzing the past trends with regard to government public spending, which is specifically intended for education, and trying of making expectations about economic growth and the growth of public spending, and determining the volume of resources that will be available to this sector in the future.
- 4- Making sector projections about the future trends of the growth of the various economic sectors in the state and their future needs of labor force, and matching that with the education's outputs with its current and future patterns, and trying to identify the deficiencies or redundant for each sector separately.

Therefore, the researcher believes that foreseeing the future of education is a basis for planning and making the educational policies and academic programs, to ensure advanced educational systems and capable to facing future challenges, and thus ensuring the survival and renaissance of their societies.

Reasons for foreseeing the future of the family and consumer sciences program in light of the requirements of vision 2030:

The political, economic and social conditions in the Kingdom seem to be in a stable pattern that encourages the optimistic planning. Despite the great maturity reached by the foreseeing studies in the developed world, and despite much talk about the future and its challenges in the Arab world, there is a noticeable lack, quantitatively and qualitatively, in Arab future studies in Education field. Al-Rasheed published his pioneering study entitled: "Among the Features of Foreseeing the Future in the Arab World in the Twenty-First Century" (Al-Rasheed, 1408), and he monitored the scarcity of the Arabic studies, and Al-Khatib followed him ten years later with a survey study of the foreseeing studies to confirm the absence of serious Arab foreseeing studies (Al-Khatib 1998 AD). However, the arena has not yet witnessed a great emergence of the future studies, and the few that have appeared have been complaining about the scarcity of data and the weakness of the analytical treatments.

The vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia by 2030 seeks to reduce the unemployment rate from 11.6% to 7%, which means that it will undoubtedly contribute to providing hundreds, perhaps thousands, of job opportunities for new graduates from various specializations.

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One of the objectives of the Kingdom's Vision 2030 is to close upon the gap between the outputs of the higher education and the requirements of the labor market. This research seeks to contribute to achieve the Kingdom's vision, as it aims to: alignment between the quality of learning outcomes in Saudi universities and the requirements of the Saudi labor market according to the vision through: determining the most important requirements of the Saudi labor market and means to develop the quality of the learning outcomes in Saudi universities according to the Kingdom's vision 2030. (Osama, Aref, 2018 AD).

In 2018 both of Osama and Aref have pointed to the most important requirements of the Saudi labor market according to the vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia 2030:

- 1- Teaching competencies.
- 2- Specialists in the field of modern and electronic commerce.

- 3- Specialists in the information technology sector.
- 4- Technical specialists to work in the mining and manufacturing sector.
- 5- Specialists in the field of renewable energy.
- 6- Specialists in the field of retail trade.
- 7- Specialists to work in the administrative sector (Business Administration) (Human Resources Department)
- 8- Specialists in the field of training
- 9- Increasing businesses and small and medium facilities.
- 10- Increasing the participation of the woman in the labor market.

The family and consumer sciences program is related to points 9 and 10, as the learning outcomes of the program qualify the graduate to establish small projects in various fields related to the skills she acquired in the program.

The general framework for foreseeing the future of the family and consumer sciences program from the researcher's view is represented as follows:

- 1- A conscious future vision of the global and local changes in the global, economic and other fields of life that lead to dealing with potential challenges and their direct effects on the labor market, and being able to develop education in line with the demands of the human development and their sustainability in the future in line with the vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia 2030.
- 2- To identify the renewable needs for economic and social development, and to prepare work and production institutions in society for the educational outputs in the future.
- 3- Foreseeing the future of education leads to a future vision that helps to set general strategic directions to develop the education, and to appropriate plans for work implemented by specific mechanisms in successive periods of time, its programs and projects are separated according to rationalizing the educational decisions with the aim of optimizing usage of the available resources.
- 4- Through the statistics of students enrolled at Umm Al-Qura University, we find that there is an increase in the number of students annually, as the number of Bachelors students for the year 1440 AH / 1441 AH reached 92178 male and female students, which makes us work for continuous planning by introducing new fields that suit the labor market. We find that the family and consumer sciences program corresponds with the requirements of the labor market and the vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia 2030.

The practical part:

The questionnaire was applied to 14 female members of the Department of Family Education at the University College in Al-Leith at Umm Al-Qura University. The following table shows their number in each specialization and their academic ranks.

Specialization	Number	Teaching Assistant	lecturer	Assistant Professor	Co-professor	Professor
Clothes and Textiles	2			1	-	1
Nutrition	7		5	2		
Administration and housing	1			1		
Art education	4		4			

The questionnaire included several axes, including:

- 1- Awareness of the basis on which the Department of Family Education relied in proposing to introduce the Family and Consumer Sciences program instead of the Family Education program.
- 2- Awareness and readiness of the concepts of foreseeing the future in your workplace.
- 3- Awareness of tools and methods of foreseeing the future applicable in your workplace.

Results and discussion:

Figure (1)

Figure (2)

We find from the graph in Figure (1) that the lowest percentage of teaching staff members was at the rank of professor by 7.1%, and the highest rank was the lecturer by 64.3%, and through the figure we note that the number of members in the Advisory Committee for Curriculum Development is 7 members by 50%. The figures show that there is sufficiency and diversity in the members and their specializations to provide multiple programs with different levels in the fields and paths of family sciences.

The first axis: awareness of the basis on which the Department of Family Education relied in proposing to introduce the Family and Consumer Sciences program instead of the Family Education program.

Figure (3)

It is clear from Figure (3) that the percentage of those who relied on some concepts of foreseeing the future in developing the program based on the university's directives that it is necessary is 42.9%, and 35.7% relied on the vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to increase the number of qualified female graduates for the labor market, and another came by 21.4%, where the results show that 42.9% relied on the concepts of foreseeing the future and 35.7% relied on the Kingdom's vision based on foreseeing the future, and thus the total becomes 78.6% who have awareness and are familiar with the requirements of the labor market and the necessary means to develop the quality of the education's outputs in Saudi universities according to vision 2030.

Figure (4)

In Figure (4), female teaching staff members expected that the program will continue by the acceptance of the female students only, with a percentage 64.3%, and we find that 35.7% expected that students will be accepted into the program in the future.

Figure (5)

From Figure (5) we find that the female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education unanimously agreed that it is necessary to study the foreseeing the future for the family and consumer sciences program in opening the field for students to qualify them for the labor market with a percentage 92.9%, and 7.1% there is no need to foreseeing the future in opening the field for students when developing the program.

The second axis: awareness and readiness of the concepts of foreseeing the future in your workplace

Figure (6)

In Figure (6) we find the difference in the views of the female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education in terms of the responsible party for foreseeing the future in the workplace, where we found an equal number of responses with a percentage 35.7% between there is no a responsible party for applying the foreseeing the future in my workplace and the management of foreseeing the future through strategic management.

Figure (7)

Figure (8)

In Figure (7), the responses of the female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education were yes, with a percentage of 57.1%, that your workplace applies procedures/methodology or a framework for foreseeing the future in developing the family education program for the Family and Consumer Sciences Program, and 42.9% answered “No” and that for many different reasons that appear in Figure (8), where the highest percentage of 36.4% stated that there are no procedures/methodology or framework for foreseeing the future in developing the family education program for the Family and Consumer Sciences Program, and a percentage 18.2% there are approved work procedures/framework regarding foreseeing the future in my workplace, but it is not implemented or partially applied, followed by 9.1% there are some practices that are applied regarding foreseeing the future in my workplace, but there is no clear framework, and 9.1% there are some efforts in the field of foreseeing the future or the existence of practices.

Figure (9)

Through Figure (9), we find that the opinion of the female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education with what the workplace does about foreseeing the future and its concepts is 42.9%. There are no efforts to raise awareness and training about the concepts of foreseeing the future in my workplace, and this percentage confirms the necessity of awareness and training of the workplace for the female teaching staff members in developing the curricula in line with the requirements of vision 2030.

Figure (10)

Through Figure (10), we find that 42.9% agreed on what the workplace is doing regarding applying qualitative methods and mechanisms to anticipate the future developments and trends.

Figure (11)

We find from Figure (11) that the evaluation of the level of awareness of the workplace with the concept of foreseeing the future came in different percentages.

Figure (12)

From Figure (12), it is clear that the readiness of the workplace to launch studies projects to foreseeing the future is medium with a percentage of 42.9%.

Figure (13)

From Figure (13), we find that with a percentage of 35.7%, the benefit of your workplace from the data to procedure the necessary analyzes to foreseeing the future is low.

Figure (14)

Through Figure (14), we find that the percentage of answering yes was 85.7% regarding your workplace from the advisory committee, foreseeing the future when developing the plans for Bachelor / Graduate Studies / Diploma programs.

The third axis: the tools and methods of foreseeing the future those are applicable in your workplace

Figure (15)

Through Figure (15), we find that the highest percentage of 42.9% was I don't know about the tools of foreseeing the future in the workplace.

Figure (16)

Figure (16) shows that 42.9% are not aware about the tools of foreseeing the future in the workplace.

Results summary:

1 - The percentage of the female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education who relied on some concepts of foreseeing the future in developing the program based on the university's directives that it is necessary is 42.9%, and the percentage of 35.7% relied on the vision of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia to increase the number of qualified female graduates for the labor market, and another came by 21.4 %.

2- The female teaching staff members expected that the program will continue to accept female students only, with a percentage of 64.3%, and we find that 35.7% expected that students will be accepted into the program in the future.

3- We find that the female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education unanimously agreed that it is necessary to study the foreseeing the future for the Family and Consumer Sciences program in opening the field for students to qualify them for the labor market, with a percentage of 92.9%.

4-There is a difference in views of the female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education in terms of the responsible party on the foreseeing the future in the workplace, where we found an equal number of responses with a percentage of 35.7% between that there is no responsible party for applying foreseeing the future in my workplace, and that foreseeing the future is managed through the strategy management.

5-The responses of the female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education were 57.1% yes, that your workplace applies procedures / methodology or a framework for foreseeing the future in the development of the family education program for the family and consumer sciences program.

6- The opinion of the female teaching staff members in the Department of Family Education about what the workplace is doing about foreseeing the future and its concepts came with a percentage of 42.9%. There are no efforts to aware and train about the concepts of foreseeing the future in my workplace. This percentage confirms the necessity of the awareness and training from the workplace for the female teaching staff members in developing curricula in line with the requirements of vision 2030.

7- The percentage of 35.7% is the benefit of your workplace from the data to procedure the necessary analyzes to foreseeing the future is low.

8- We find that the highest percentage 42.9% was I do not know about the tools of the foreseeing the future in the workplace, to 42.9% regarding the tools of the foreseeing the future in the workplace.

Recommendations:

1- Finding a unit for foreseeing the future for the family and consumer sciences program.

2- The family and consumer sciences program must be taught to students and not limited to female students due to the diversity of the fields of the labor market. The continued growth in the demand for education in the future (indicating the increase in the number of students in the future) requires continuing the effort to meet the demand with an educational service at the desired quality level. So, increasing the number of male and female students at high rates requires planning to convert the Department of Family and Consumer Sciences to a college that matches this percentage, as well as equipping the buildings with all the needs to achieve quality learning outcomes for the labor market.

3- Using technology in teaching students by introducing the "Education without Borders" initiative to increase the number of students for the theoretical courses.

- 4- Opening paid graduate studies programs for the Family and Consumer Sciences program in the branch faculties.
- 5- Finding more positive solutions, as there is no clear policy to foreseeing the future for the family and consumer sciences program that necessitates the need to support research projects that help to discover them.
- 6- The current study also raised the importance of procedure studies related to foreseeing the future for the academic programs with the continuation of the process of development and improvement, and that helps in better planning of the educational policies.
- 7- Spreading the culture of foreseeing the future of the academic programs for the teaching staff members.
- 8- Following the mechanism and methods of foreseeing the future in a sufficient period of time before approving stop the admission to the department, which causes harm to the female teaching staff members due to the lack of teaching quorum.
- 9- Involve all members of the department in foreseeing the future of the department to qualify a generation of specialists in foreseeing the future of the academic programs.

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